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Neural correlates of visual awareness at stimulus low vs. high-levels of processing

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Abstract

A crucial view in the graded vs. dichotomous debate on visual awareness proposes that its graded or dichotomous nature may depend on the depth of stimulus processing (or *level of processing*) associated to the experimental task. In the present study, we explored the behavioral patterns and neural correlates of different degrees of awareness associated to different depths (i.e. low vs. high) of stimulus processing. The low-level stimulus condition consisted of detecting the location of the target based on its brightness characteristics, whereas the high-level stimulus condition consisted of identifying which of four possible targets (numbers/letters) had appeared. Behavioral results showed that both subjective ratings of awareness and accuracy levels increased linearly as a function of awareness and independently of the level of stimulus processing. Additionally, the electrophysiological recordings revealed two correlates of visual awareness: enhanced posterior negativity in the N200 time window (VAN, *visual awareness negativity*) and enhanced positivity in the P3 time window (LP, *late positivity*). Interestingly, we found evidence of awareness levels modulating N200/VAN amplitudes in a graded manner only for the low-level task, whereas P3/LP amplitudes were modulated in a graded manner for both low and high-level tasks. The finding that the early posterior correlate of visual awareness (VAN at 150-250 ms) was sensitive to level of processing is consistent with task effects occurring in the visual cortex and supports the view that it is mediated by attention to task-relevant features. The amplitudes of P3/LP in both tasks correlate more directly with graded awareness and behavioral accuracy.

1. Introduction

A recent approach within consciousness research tries to understand the fundamental nature of visual awareness, the subjective experience of seeing. Whereas some studies suggest that visual awareness is an all-or-none phenomena (Asplund, Fournie, Zughni, Martin, & Marois, 2014; Del Cul, Baillet, & Dehaene, 2007, Sergent & Dehaene, 2004; Sekar, Findley, Poeppel, & Llinás, 2013), others propose that it develops gradually through different degrees of subjective awareness (Overgaard, Rote, Mouridsen, & Ramsøy, 2006; Pretorius, Tredoux, & Malcolm-Smith, 2016; Ramsøy, & Overgaard, 2004; Seth, Dienes, Cleeremans, Overgaard, & Pessoa, 2008). Interestingly, while some of the experiments in search of the neural correlates of consciousness (NCC, or the minimum neural mechanisms sufficient for a specific conscious percept; Koch, Massimini, Boly, & Tononi, 2016) contrasts the ERPs associated to “seen” vs. “not seen” conditions, research on the graded vs. all-or-none nature of awareness tries to capture observers’ intermediate awareness experiences by using more exhaustive report measures which introduce different visibility categories such as “brief glimpse” or “almost clear experience”. Commonly, a four-point scale (*PAS, Perceptual Awareness Scale*; Ramsøy & Overgaard, 2004) is considered the most exhaustive measure for capturing different degrees of visual awareness as well as producing a good correlation between performance and awareness (Pretorius et al., 2016; Sandberg, Timmermans, Overgaard, & Cleeremans, 2010).

However, few are the studies which have used subjective visibility scales to explore the neural underpinnings of different degrees of visual awareness. Tagliabue, Mazzi, Bagattini and Savazzi (2016) recently conducted a study to explore ERPs in response to reduced contrast visual stimuli, where participants had to judge the brightness of the stimuli (light vs. dark) and then qualitatively rate their visual experiences in a 4-point awareness scale. Consistent with previous findings on the NCC (Del Cul et al., 2007; Koivisto & Grassini, 2016; Koivisto, Grassini, Salminen-Vaparanta and Revonsuo, 2017; Koivisto, Salminen-Vaparanta, Grassini, & Revonsuo, 2016; Rutiku, Aru, & Bachmann, 2016), their ERP results revealed two electrophysiological components correlating with visual awareness: a negative early deflection (also termed *visual awareness negativity*, VAN) peaking at 280-320 ms at lateral, parietal and central sites in the left hemisphere, followed by a bilateral positive deflection (*late positivity*, LP) peaking at 510-550 ms over all electrodes. Moreover, the amplitude of both deflections gradually increased as a function of visual awareness, thus the authors concluded that visual perceptual experience is characterized by a gradual increase in

awareness at both behavioral (accuracies) and neural (amplitudes) levels.

A crucial view in the graded vs. dichotomous nature of visual awareness proposes that its graded or dichotomous nature may depend on the depth of stimulus processing (or *level of processing*) associated to the experimental task (Kouider, De Gardelle, Sackur, & Dupoux, 2010). According to this view, a “higher-level” stimulus processing (such as the perception of letters, words or meaning) would produce more dichotomously distributed subjective experiences, while a “lower-level” stimulus processing (i.e., the perception of the stimulus at its basic energy or feature levels) would yield a more graded emergence of visual awareness (Windey & Cleeremans, 2015). Previous behavioral studies have used lower vs. higher-level stimulus processing and found some evidence supporting this interpretation (Anzulewicz, Asanowicz, Windey, Paulewicz, Wierzchoń, & Cleeremans, 2015; Windey, Gevers, & Cleeremans, 2013). Recently, an fMRI study (Binder et al., 2017) found that the manipulation of levels of processing influenced brain activity in posterior visual areas, suggesting that the level of processing effect on awareness may be mediated by an attentional top-down modulation of activity in visual regions.

Yet, to our knowledge, no previous study has comprehensively explored the ERP correlates of different degrees of awareness associated to different depths (i.e. low vs. high) of stimulus processing. In the present work, we explored and compared the ERPs associated to different degrees of awareness at both low and high-level stimulus processing conditions. In the detection task, participants had to report in which of the four quadrants the target had appeared, a low-level task that could be accomplished based on the low-level features of the targets (i.e. luminance differences between target and background). In the identification task, the observers had to inform which of the four targets had appeared, a higher level task that was based on higher level stimulus characteristics (i.e. at letter/number level of representation; Kouider et al., 2010). In order to produce different visibility levels, we manipulated the strength of the masking by varying the stimulus-mask onset asynchrony (SOA) as well as the mask’s degree of organization. This experimental design has been recently successful in producing different subjective awareness at individual SOAs (Jimenez, Villalba-García, Luna, Hinojosa, & Montoro, submitted for publication), following the evidence which suggest a link between the global regularity of the mask and the masking strength (Ghose, Hermens, & Herzog, 2012; Hermens, & Herzog, 2007). Subjective awareness of the target was reported on a 4-scale rating scale adapted from the PAS scale (Ramsøy & Overgaard, 2004). The four possible ratings were: 1) *no perception*, 2) *weak*

perception, 3) *almost clear perception*, and 4) *clear perception*.

Following previous EEG evidence (Tagliabue et al., 2016), and in accordance with the *levels of processing* hypothesis (Windey & Cleeremans, 2015), we expected low-level stimulus perception (i.e. detection task at stimulus energy level of representation) to produce a significant number of intermediate subjective awareness ratings, a gradual increase in accuracy levels across the awareness scale, and a linear increase in ERP amplitudes as a function of the degrees of awareness. On the other hand, we expected higher-level stimulus processing (i.e. identification of letters/numbers) to produce a more dichotomously distributed subjective awareness ratings and accuracy levels and, crucially, a non-linear increase of the ERP amplitudes as a function of the degrees of awareness.

2. Methods

2.1. Participants

Sixteen right-handed students (9 women, age range = 20–34 years, $M = 25$; $SD = 4.38$) with normal or corrected-to-normal vision took part in the present study. The sample size was determined on the basis of our earlier studies that had used similar methods on studying electrophysiological correlates of visual awareness (Koivisto & Grassini, 2016; Koivisto, et al., 2017). The experiment was conducted with the understanding and written consent of each participant, in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki, and accepted by the ethics committee of the Hospital District of Southwest Finland.

2.2. Stimuli and apparatus

The stimuli were displayed on a 19-in. LCD monitor with a 75 Hz refresh rate, a 5:4 aspect ratio and a resolution of 1280 x 1024 controlled by a computer running E-Prime 2.0 software (Psychology Software Tools, 1996–2002). Viewing distance was approximately 150 cm.

The target stimuli were composed of a grid of 20 x 20 local elements (dots), each dot subtending a visual angle of 0.2° (see Fig 1.a). The target “6” was composed of fourteen clear dots (23.52 cd/m^2), whereas the target “9” was generated by rotating the target “6” by 180° . The target “H” was composed of thirteen clear dots (23.52 cd/m^2), whereas the target “I” was generated by rotating the target “H” by 90° . The widest side of all targets subtended a visual angle of 1.8° . Targets appeared in one of the four quadrants of the grid. The center of the target in each quadrant was at 2.8° from the center of the screen. In the center of the three quadrants where the target did not appear, a clear (23.52 cd/m^2) dot appeared at 2.8° from the center of the screen. The remaining dots of the grid were of dark luminance (0.30 cd/m^2). A

number of catch trials (the grid with no target, see Fig. 1b) were introduced in order to verify that participants were correctly following the instructions, as well as to get “only-mask” ERP waves.

The masks were composed of a grid of 20 x 20 local elements (dots), half of them of clear luminance and the other half of dark luminance. There were five different mask types based on their degree of organization (90%, 80%, 70%, 60% and 50% organization). The organization of the masks was manipulated in both the vertical and the horizontal axis: the most organized masks (90% organization) were arranged into columns and rows, where 90 % of the dots (i.e. 18 out of 20) were of the same of the same luminance. More irregular masks where generated by introducing opposite luminance dots into each column/row: 80% organization masks had 80% same brightness dots in each column/row, 70% organization masks had 70% same brightness dots in each column/row, etc. Eventually, in the 50% organization mask, the different brightness dots were randomly distributed across the mask (see Fig. 1c). Each mask was created by gluing together four sub-masks randomly assigned to each quadrant of the stimulus (see Fig. 1d), a manipulation intended to create effective and homogenous masking conditions across all four grid quadrants. There were four different sub-masks to be assigned for each mask organization, two in the vertical axis and two in the horizontal axis. Therefore, there were twenty-four mask variations for each organization (90% to 50%) for a total of one hundred and twenty possible masks.

Insert Fig. 1

2.2. Procedure and design

Two tasks (detection and identification) were performed by participants in a counterbalanced order. In both tasks, each trial began with an initial (“ready?”) screen for 800 ms, after which a “3-2-1 countdown” followed. After that, a grey screen appeared for 200 ms (see Fig. 2), which was followed by the target (or a catch-trial). The targets were shown for 13 or 27 ms in the detection task and for 27 or 40 ms in the identification task. The target durations were based on informal pilot tests conducted prior to the formal experiments. Because the mask was presented immediately after the offset of the target, the target-mask stimulus onset asynchronies (SOAs) were 13 and 27 ms in the detection task and 27 and 40 ms in the

identification task. Each target stimulus appeared equally often, but in random order, in each four possible target locations and at each SOA. A control stimulus was used in 10% of the trials in both tasks, consisting of the targets being shown for a long duration of 107 ms. The target was followed by the mask for a variable duration (see Fig. 2a and Fig. 2b) to maintain the duration of the target-mask combination fixed at a duration of 706 ms. In the forced-choice detection task, participants indicated the target location by clicking with the mouse on one of the four possible quadrants that were displayed (see Fig. 2a). In the forced-choice identification task, participants indicated which of the targets had appeared by clicking with the mouse on one of the four horizontally-oriented rectangles (see Fig. 2b). The forced-choice task was followed by the subjective awareness screen, where participants indicated in both tasks their subjective awareness by clicking with the mouse on one of the four possible rating level alternatives. The names of the rating levels were displayed in four horizontally-oriented rectangles, which ranged from 1) *no perception* to 4) *clear perception*, being the intermediate options 2) *weak perception* and 3) *almost clear perception*. A blank, inter-trial screen then appeared for 800 ms. Each task started with a practice block of 8 trials followed by four blocks of 110 trials each, yielding a total of 440 experimental trials in each task, of which 100 were catch trials and 40 control trials.

Insert Fig. 2

2.3. EEG recordings and data analysis

The EEG signal was continuously recorded using a cap with sintered Ag/AgCl active electrodes (Easycap GmbH, Herrsching, Germany) from 64 scalp sites positioned according to the 10-10 electrode system. Data collection was carried out using NeurOne 1.3.1.26 software and Tesla #MRI 2013011 and #MRI 2013012 amplifiers (Mega Electronics Ltd, Kuopio, Finland). Signal was referenced online to Cz and the ground electrode was placed on AFz. Blinks and eye movements were monitored using four additional bipolar electrodes. The recording sampling rate was 500 Hz.

The processing of the EEG data was performed offline with the EEGLAB toolbox version 14.1.1 (Delorme & Makeig, 2004) using MATLAB scripts (v. R2014b; The MathWorks, Inc., Natick, MA). Data were down-sampled to 250 Hz and high-pass filtered at 0.1 Hz, using a Hamming windowed-sinc FIR filter (EEGLAB function “pop_eegfiltnew.m”). Afterwards,

a low-pass 30Hz filter was applied in order to attenuate line noise, and eye channels were removed from the data. Artifacts in the continuous EEG recording and bad electrodes were then removed or attenuated using the Artifact Subspace Reconstruction method from the Clean Rawdata EEGLAB plug-in (EEGLAB function “clean_rawdata”, Kothe, 2013; Piazza et al., 2016). Data were then re-referenced to the average of all the electrodes, and epoched (-300 to 800 ms from stimulus onset), then, baseline correction was applied from -200 to 0 ms before the onset of the stimulus. Segments containing artifacts were rejected (EEGLAB function pop_rejkurt.m). In order to identify and subsequently remove eye-blink, eye-movement, heart-beat artifacts and other non-neural activity in the data, the data were submitted to the extended Infomax independent component analysis (ICA, EEGLAB function “pop_runica.m”). ADJUST 1.1.1 (EEGLAB function “ADJUST.m”, Mognon, Jovicich, Bruzzone, & Buiatti, 2011; Pontifex, Miskovic, & Laszlo, 2017) was used to identify and eliminate artefactual ICs. Finally, the bad electrodes were interpolated using spherical interpolation (EEGLAB function pop_interpolate.m).

In order to avoid target duration confounds in the analysis of the ERPs, only the data for identical physical stimulation (i.e. SOA 27 ms in both tasks) was analyzed. ERPs were averaged separately for each awareness rating at each SOA condition for both the detection and the identification tasks. Due to the small number of trials where participants used rating 4 (*clear perception*), awareness ratings 3 (*almost clear perception*) and 4 (*clear perception*) were pooled in both tasks. Therefore, three different ERPs were obtained at each SOA and task (i.e. ERP-1: *no perception*, ERP-2: *weak perception*, ERP-3: *almost clear/clear perception*). Catch trials were averaged per SOA condition in each task, which produced mask-only ERPs. The mask-only ERP was subtracted from the averaged ERPs for each awareness condition at each SOA, producing a target-only ERP for each awareness rating (see Fig. 3). These ERPs were submitted to the statistical EEG analyses described in part 3.2.

Insert Fig. 3

3. Results

3.1. Behavioural

In the detection task, the distribution of awareness ratings concentrated in the *unaware end* of

the scale¹ in the shortest SOA of 13 ms (see Table 1 and Fig. 4a), whereas *intermediate ratings* were reported in 31% of the trials (see Fig. 4b). In the longer SOA of 27 ms, the different rating categories were more evenly used (see Table 1 and Fig. 3a), intermediate ratings being reported in 51% of the trials (see Fig. 4b). When catch-trials were presented, participants reported *no perception* (rating 1) in most of the trials (SOA 13 ms, 78% of the trials; SOA 27 ms, in 73% of the trials). The control stimulus (SOA of 106 ms), on the other hand, produced the expected pattern of *almost clear* and *clear perception* reports (rating 3 was used in 13% of the trials and rating 4 in 82% of the trials).

In the identification task, the distribution of awareness ratings skewed towards the *unaware end* of the scale at SOA of 27 ms (see Table 1 and Fig. 4c), while *intermediate ratings* were reported in 53% of the trials (see Fig. 4d). In the longer SOA of 40 ms, the distribution concentrated in the center of the scale (see Table 1 and Fig. 4c), *intermediate ratings* being reported in 67% of the trials (see Fig. 4d). When catch-trials were presented, participants reported *no perception* (rating 1) in most of the trials (SOA 27 ms: 84% of the trials; SOA 40 ms: 79% of the trials). The control stimulus (i.e., SOA 106 ms), in contrast, produced the expected pattern of *almost clear* and *clear perception* reports (rating 3 was used in 18% of the trials, rating 4 in 76% of the trials).

 Insert Table 1

To explore differences in the distribution of the awareness ratings at the shared SOA of 27 ms between the two tasks, a 2 (Task: Detection vs. Identification) x 4 (Awareness Rating: 1 – *no perception*–, 2 –*weak perception*–, 3 –*almost clear perception*– and 4, –*clear perception*–) repeated measures ANOVA and a further *t*-test on aggregated intermediate ratings were conducted. If the distribution of awareness ratings at the higher-level (i.e. identification) task followed a more dichotomous pattern, we would expect increased rating 1 (*no perception*) and rating 4 (*clear perception*) reports, and significantly fewer number of intermediate ratings (aggregated ratings 2 and 3). ANOVA results showed a significant main effect for Awareness Rating ($F(3,45) = 33.90$, $MSe = 642.01$, $p < .001$, $\eta^2_p = .69$), suggesting that the

¹ Note that we will refer to the *unaware end* of the scale as the aggregated ratings 1 and 2, *intermediate ratings* as the aggregated ratings 2 and 3 and the *aware end* of the scale as the aggregated ratings 3 and 4.

different ratings were not uniformly used (mean number of trials at each awareness category: rating 1 = 59, rating 2 = 50, rating 3 = 29, rating 4 = 12). A significant Task x Awareness Rating interaction ($F(3,45) = 3.60$, $MSe = 162.24$, $p < .05$, $\eta^2_p = .19$) suggested different awareness rating distributions between tasks. Post-hoc comparisons showed no differences between tasks for rating 1 (*no perception*; $p = .194$), only a marginal effect for rating 2 (*weak perception*; $p = .059$), no differences for rating 3 (*almost clear perception*; $p = .142$) and significant differences for rating 4 (*clear perception*; $p < .01$), being *clear perceptions* less reported in the higher level task (see Table 1). Further comparison with *t*-test for *intermediate* reports showed no significant differences for intermediate awareness ratings ($t(15) = -.541$; $p = .596$) (see Fig. 4e). Results overall suggest that awareness reports at the higher-level task did not follow a more dichotomous distribution.

In sum, the distribution of awareness reports in the detection task was concentrated in the *unaware end* of the scale for the shortest SOA of 13 ms, showing that this condition very rarely produced *almost clear* or *clear perception* experiences. However, the longer SOA of 27 ms produced a significant number of intermediate ratings: ratings 2 and 3 were reported in 51% of the trials, which is in line with expected graded awareness experience for low-level stimulus processing. On the other hand, the distribution of awareness reports in the identification task showed a significant number of intermediate ratings at both the SOA of 27 ms (53% of the trials) and the SOA of 40 ms (67% of the trials). Furthermore, a between-task ANOVA at SOA 27 ms and a *t*-test showed that there were no significant differences for the mean use of intermediate awareness ratings between tasks. Contrary to the levels of processing predictions, here we found evidence that higher-level stimulus processing at word/letter level of representation produced a graded pattern of awareness.

In order to explore the relation between detection and identification accuracies and the subjective awareness of the stimulus, a one-way repeated measures ANOVA was conducted for accuracy levels at each category of the awareness scale at each SOA in each task. Results for the detection task showed that increasing visual awareness produced linearly increasing accuracy levels (SOA 13 ms: $F(3,33) = 76.94$, $MSe = .19$, $p < .001$, $\eta^2_p = .87$, linear trend $F(1,11) = 441.23$, $MSe = .01$, $p < .001$, $\eta^2_p = .97$; SOA 27 ms: $F(3,42) = 152.75$, $MSe = .01$, $p < .001$, $\eta^2_p = .91$, linear trend $F(1,14) = 877.03$, $MSe = .004$, $p < .001$, $\eta^2_p = .98$) (see Table 1 and Fig. 5a and 5b). Results for the identification task also showed that increasing visual awareness produced linearly increasing accuracy levels (SOA 27 ms: $F(3,45) = 139.44$, $MSe = .011$, $p < .001$, $\eta^2_p = .90$, linear trend $F(1,11) = 441.13$, $MSe = .010$, $p < .001$, $\eta^2_p = .97$;

SOA 40 ms: $F(3,45) = 189.06$, $MSe = .01$, $p < .001$, $\eta^2_p = .93$, linear trend $F(1,15) = 635.58$, $MSe = .008$, $p < .001$, $\eta^2_p = .98$ (see Table 1 and Fig. 5c and 5d). In sum, accuracy levels increased following a linear trend at stimulus lower level of representation (i.e. detection task), in line with the *levels of processing* hypothesis. In addition, accuracy levels also increased following a very clear gradual pattern at the letter/number level of representation (i.e. identification task), results that did not follow the expected more dichotomous pattern of awareness at the higher-level of stimulus processing.

Insert Figures 4 and 5

3.2. EEG

Based on visual inspection of grand-average ERPs and their scalp maps, N200/VAN peaked in the 150-250 ms time-window in occipital electrodes (O1, O2, PO7, PO8) and P3/LP in the 350-450 ms time window in parietal-occipital electrodes (P3, P4, PO3, PO4), as expected. Therefore, a 2 (Task: detection vs identification) x 2 (Area: occipital vs parietal-occipital) x 3 (Awareness: 1, 2 and combined 3-4) repeated-measures ANOVA on the mean amplitudes (Fig.6) was separately conducted for each time window.

Insert Figure 6

3.2.1. 150-250 ms (N200/VAN)

In the VAN time-window, a main effect for Area [$F(1,15) = 30.38$, $MSe = .68$, $p < .001$, $\eta^2_p = .67$] showed that N200 peaked in occipital area. A main effect for Awareness, $F(2,30) = 21.16$, $MSe = 1.64$, $p < .001$, $\eta^2_p = .58$, indicated increasing negativity in amplitudes for increasing awareness. In addition, Area interacted with Awareness [$F(1,21) = 25.11$, $MSe = .36$, $p < .001$, $\eta^2_p = .63^2$], showing that increased negativity for increasing levels of awareness peaked at occipital cluster. Crucially, Task interacted with Awareness, $F(2,30) = 10.81$, $MSe = .61$, $p < .01$, $\eta^2_p = .42$, suggesting differences in the amplitudes associated to each

² Greenhouse-Geisser corrections were applied on p-values and degrees of freedom when the sphericity assumption was violated.

awareness rating between tasks. Pairwise comparisons³ confirmed that the three awareness categories produced significantly different amplitudes in the detection task, being the amplitude associated to the combined ratings 3 and 4 significantly larger than the amplitude associated to rating 2 ($p < .01$) and rating 1 ($p < .001$), and the amplitude associated to rating 2 significantly larger than the amplitude associated to rating 1 ($p < .001$) (see Fig. 6). In the identification task, significant differences were found between the amplitude associated to awareness ratings 1 and 2 ($p < .001$) and awareness rating 1 and combined ratings 3 and 4, but there were no differences in the amplitudes between awareness rating 2 and combined ratings 3-4 ($p = 1.00$) (see Fig. 6). Thus, consistent with the *levels of processing* hypothesis, the low-level processing (detection task) linearly modulated the amplitudes at VAN time-window, whereas higher-level perception (identification task) produced a non-linear increase in the amplitudes associated to the different degrees of awareness.

3.2.2. 350-450 ms (P3/LP)

In the LP time-window, a main effect for Area [$F(1,15) = 27.28$, $MSe = .60$, $p < .001$, $\eta^2_p = .64$] showed that P3 peaked in occipital-parietal area. A significant effect for Awareness, $F(1,20) = 15.38$, $MSe = 2.46$, $p < .001$, $\eta^2_p = .51$ showed that increasing awareness of the stimuli elicited larger positivity in the ERP amplitudes. In addition, Area interacted with Awareness [$F(2,30) = 33.48$, $MSe = .27$, $p < .001$, $\eta^2_p = .69^2$] showing that increased positivity for increasing awareness levels peaked at occipital-parietal cluster. Importantly, Task did not interact with Awareness $F(2,30) = 2.05$, $MSe = 1.19$, $p = .146$, $\eta^2_p = .12$). A significant linear trend for Awareness [$F(1,15) = 16.92$, $MSe = 2.73$, $p < .01$, $\eta^2_p = .53$] showed that the amplitudes associated to the different degrees of awareness followed a linear increase in both the detection and the identification tasks (see Fig. 6), and therefore they correlated with the observed behavioral output (accuracy).⁴

4. Discussion

³ All pairwise comparisons were conducted using Bonferroni correction.

⁴ In order to explore if the obtained results were influenced by the mask subtraction method, we conducted the same ANOVA analyses for the *target+mask* data. Statistical analyses showed the same pattern of results. In the VAN time-window, a main effect was found for Awareness [$F(2,30) = 33.183$, $MSe = 1.04$, $p < .001$, $\eta^2_p = .68$] and Task interacted with Awareness [$F(2,30) = 8.015$, $MSe = .40$, $p < .01$, $\eta^2_p = .35$]. Pairwise comparisons replicated the results obtained for the subtracted data. In the LP time-window, a main effect for awareness was found $F(1,18) = 34.562$, $MSe = 1.47$, $p < .001$, $\eta^2_p = .70$ but no second order interaction. Again, a significant linear trend was found for Awareness [$F(1,15) = 38.626$, $MSe = 1.58$, $p < .001$, $\eta^2_p = .72$].

In the present study, we explored the behavioral patterns and neural correlates of different degrees of visual awareness associated to different depths (i.e. low vs. high) of stimulus processing. The low-level stimulus condition consisted of detecting the location of the target based on its brightness characteristics (i.e. stimulus detection at energy level of representation), whereas the high-level stimulus condition consisted of identifying which of four possible targets (numbers/letters) had appeared (i.e. stimulus identification at letter/number level of representation; Kouider et al., 2010). Behavioral results showed that both subjective ratings of awareness and accuracy levels increased linearly as a function of awareness and independent of the level of processing of the stimulus. Additionally, the electrophysiological recordings revealed two correlates of visual awareness: enhanced posterior negativity in the N200 time window (VAN) and enhanced positivity in the P3 time window (LP). Only VAN was sensitive to the level of processing task manipulation, whereas the amplitude LP increased linearly as a function of awareness ratings.

Specifically, and following the *levels of processing* hypothesis (Windey & Cleeremans, 2015), we expected low-level stimulus processing to produce a significant number of intermediate subjective awareness ratings and a gradual increase in accuracy levels across the awareness scale. This was confirmed by the awareness rating distributions and accuracy levels in the detection task: even though the rating distribution was concentrated in the *unaware end* of the scale at the very restrictive SOA of 13 ms, participants reported intermediate awareness experiences (combined ratings 2 and 3) in 51% of the trials in the longer SOA of 27 ms (see Table 1 and Figs. 4a and 4b). On the other hand, accuracy increased as a function of awareness at both SOAs (see Table 1 and Figs. 5a and 5b). Also in accordance with the *levels of processing* hypothesis, we expected the higher-level task to produce a more dichotomously distributed subjective awareness ratings and accuracy levels. Contrary to this prediction, both the distribution of awareness ratings and the increase in accuracy levels showed a clear gradual pattern in the identification task. Participants reported intermediate awareness experiences (ratings 2 and 3) in 53% of the trials in the SOA 27 ms and in 67% of the trials in SOA 40 ms (see Table 1 and Figs. 4c and 4d). Moreover, there were no significant differences between tasks in the mean use of intermediate awareness ratings (see Fig. 4e). In addition, accuracy levels also increased gradually as a function of SOA in the identification task (see Table 1 and Figs. 5c and 5d).

Interestingly, the electrophysiological correlates for the different degrees of awareness showed a dissociation between low and high-level stimulus processing. The low-level

processing (i.e. detection task) linearly modulated the amplitudes at VAN (N200) time-window over occipital areas, while higher-level stimulus perception (i.e. identification task) elicited a non-linear increase in the amplitudes. The gradual amplitude deflections as a function of visual awareness at low-level stimulus processing are consistent with the *levels of processing* hypothesis and with recent results by Tagliabue et al. (2016), whom also found an amplitude modulation for increasing degrees of awareness at the VAN time-window for low-level stimulus perception. The pattern of results obtained at the VAN time-window are also in line with previous findings by Koivisto et al. (2017), who presented participants with very brief low contrast stimuli in a stimulus detection and a more complex digit identification and comparison task. Their results showed a significant amplitude difference between aware and unaware trials in the low-level detection task (i.e. rating 1 vs. rating 2) at the VAN time-window (around 200 ms), but VAN did not correlate with higher-level awareness in the identification task, operationalized as the amplitude difference between “saw something” and “saw almost clearly” (i.e., ratings 2 vs. 3). In other words, the findings in the present study and in Koivisto et al. (2017) suggest that the microgenesis of conscious perception (Bachmann, 2000) proceeds from an early elementary phenomenal sensation of *something appearing*, as indexed by VAN, to a full-blown conscious perception of the stimulus’ higher-level properties, as indexed by the P3/LP in later latency range. VAN is assumed to reflect feedback activity in the visual cortex (Koivisto & Revonsuo, 2010), which is an important mechanism distinguishing conscious perception from unconscious processing that can be based on feedforward activation only (Lamme, 2010). The result that VAN is sensitive to the level of processing of the stimulus converges with previous fMRI findings showing that activity in the visual cortex correlates with the level of processing manipulation (Binder et al., 2017). In Binder et al.’s (2017) work, the low-level task recruited visual (early and ventral) areas, whereas in the high-level task, these visual regions became active only at the two highest levels of subjective visibility, suggesting a different processing of the target stimuli at increasing levels of visibility in this task. The authors explained their findings in terms of attentional (feedback) modulation of early visual areas. Interestingly, our higher-level task was more demanding than the lower-level task and thus required additional attention to the targets in order to discriminate and identify them. Attention can enhance/amplify feedback activity in early visual areas, as suggested by previous evidence (see Carrasco, 2011, for a review). Accordingly, attentional involvement in the identification task may have modulated the ERP waves, and in VAN time window this was reflected as an enhancement of the awareness levels associated to the target’s low-level features

(corresponding to rating 2), but not to target's higher level features (corresponding to rating 3). Furthermore, this kind of attentional mechanisms may have produced a criterion shift in the use of the awareness scale, which is discussed below.

On the other hand, the LP has been suggested to correlate with access to global neuronal workspace (Dehaene & Changeux, 2011), or reflective consciousness (Koivisto & Revonsuo, 2010), which allow higher-level cognitive operations and conscious reports of the perceived contents. Consistent with this account, in the P3/LP time-window the amplitudes associated to the different degrees of awareness followed a linear increase in both the detection and the identification tasks in occipital-parietal areas, and they interestingly correlated with the observed behavioral output (accuracy). It has been argued that conscious access to higher properties of the stimulus and post-perceptual or decision-making processes correlate with the later P3 component (Koivisto et al., 2017; Koivisto et al., 2016; Koivisto & Revonsuo, 2010; Pitts, Padwal, Fennelly, Martínez, & Hillyard, 2014). A previous ERP study that used a continuous awareness scale and a task involving decision-making processes (i.e. comparing numbers as either higher or lower than 5) found that the distribution of accuracy levels for increasing target-mask SOAs was dichotomous (Del Cul et al., 2007). When ERPs were averaged at each SOA in Del Cul et al.'s work, the P3 was the only component whose amplitude varied with a similar non-linear trend to accuracy levels. Conversely, in the present study, the higher-level task only required stimulus identification, as opposed to higher cognitive and decision-making processes (such as comparison of meanings) involved in Del Cul et al. (2007). Thus, when decision-making processes at high-level conceptual levels are absent from the experimental design, behavioral (accuracy) and P3 amplitudes seem to fit with a more gradual pattern, as suggested by the findings in the present study and in Tagliabue et al. (2016). This pattern of results seems to be consistent with the interpretation of the P3 correlating with the behavioral output, as a measure of later reflective and decision-making processes performed on the stimuli. Furthermore, P3 has been proposed to index confidence in one's decision (Eimer & Mazza, 2005; Nieuwenhuis, Aston-Jones, & Cohen, 2005), which might also play a part in explaining the P3 results obtained in the present study. On the other hand, it could be argued that graded P3 results at the higher-level identification task are modulated by the same attentional component that influenced weak perceptions at VAN time-window. In other words, if attentional involvement is necessary to boost weak percepts in order to perform a high-level identification task, this attentional amplification may have its own ERP component that may overlap VAN and subsequently influence the

measurement of the ERP waves at P3. Assuming that such negative-going ERP would persist into the P3 time frame and influence weak perception ERPs only, this would result in a modulation leading to a graded pattern of ERP results in the P3 time-window. However, contrary to this hypothesis, amplitudes associated to the different degrees of awareness continued to follow a linear increase at a more central electrode cluster (i.e. C3, C4, CP3, CP4; see Fig. S1 in supplementary material). Interestingly, the ERPs at VAN time-window had switched polarity (now being of positive magnitude), overall suggesting that a negative-going attention related ERP component was not responsible for the graded P3 amplitudes.

Although we did not observe any support for the level of processing account in the behavioral responses, we found some evidence for different distribution of awareness ratings between the tasks. Compared to the results of the detection task in the 27 SOA condition, significantly fewer “clear” percepts were reported in the identification task, together with a higher number of “weak” perceptions. Whereas participants performed two different objective tasks (detection and identification), the same graded awareness scale was used during both tasks. Because “clarity” is not exhaustively defined in the awareness scale, it may be possible that the criterion contents for reporting awareness levels changed to some extent following the criterion contents used in the objective task (Bachmann, 2015; Sackur, 2013). The objective identification task required the perception of the shape of the targets which involved additional attention to target features not required in the detection task, and therefore the awareness ratings were likely based on the contents that are essential for identifying the target (i.e., the clarity of the shape). In the detection task, participants had only to locate the target. Here, “almost clear” and “clear” ratings may have been used to refer to the clarity of perceiving the target in one of the quadrants, yet without evaluating the clarity of the perceived shape as much as in the identification task⁵. Accordingly, equally large N200 amplitudes for “weak” and “almost/clear” perceptions in the identification task suggest that VAN would not be sensitive to differences related to higher-level visual processes such as differences in the clarity of shape recognitions, but it is sensitive to different clarity levels (i.e. awareness ratings) at the most basic appearance/energy of the stimulus. As proposed above, attentional (feedback) activity may be one of the process modulating differences in

⁵ Note that participants were instructed on how to use the PAS scale before the experiment started. However, this does not rule out the possibility that some participants may have shifted their criterion according to the contents used in the objective task. We encourage for a thorough control on the use of PAS scale in future research, especially when different depths of stimulus processing are being used.

ERPs at VAN time-window between tasks.

Of note, the differences in the distribution of awareness ratings between tasks at the 27 ms SOA might alternatively reflect a criterion shift as a result of the different SOAs used in both tasks (detection: 13 vs. 27 ms; identification: 27 vs. 40 ms). Because the tasks were performed in separate blocks, the stimuli at the SOA of 27 ms in the identification task were perceived less clearly than the stimuli at the SOA of 40 ms, leading to the exaggeration of the lower-end ratings at the 27 ms SOA. In the detection task, the stimuli at the 27 ms SOA were perceived more clearly than in the shorter 13 ms SOA, biasing the ratings toward the higher end at the longer 27 ms SOA. On the other hand, SOA manipulation has been a common procedure in behavioral studies of visual awareness to obtain variation in the subjective ratings of awareness (Anzulewicz et al., 2015; Overgaard et al., 2006; Pretorius et al., 2016; Windey et al., 2013).

To our knowledge, here we found the first evidence of a higher-level stimulus perception producing a graded pattern of visual awareness. How could these findings integrate with the previous evidence? According to the *levels of processing* view (Windey & Cleeremans, 2015), low-level visual experience should be regarded as gradual as low-level stimuli would be non-semantic in nature, and therefore they cannot typically be associated to a single, clear, lexical label. Higher-level stimuli, such as letters, numbers and words, on the other hand, would typically represent one precise concept producing a clear boundary between one concept and another; therefore, in this sense, higher-level cognition may be considered as dichotomous. The present findings may be reconciled with the *levels of processing* framework by postulating that the more dichotomous nature of visual experience would only emerge at the highest-level of stimulus processing, i.e. with stimuli and tasks requiring access to meaning. Conversely, it could be argued that more dichotomous results are influenced by the nature of the task. When the task to be performed on high-level stimuli involves complex post-perceptual cognitive processes, such as stimulus comparison, conceptual judgements and decision-making processes (i.e. judging numbers as either higher or lower) behavioral results seem to follow a more dichotomous pattern, as measured by more dichotomous awareness reports and a non-linear increase in accuracy levels across the awareness scale (see Windey, Vermeiren, Atas, & Cleeremans, 2014, for a review). It seems possible, however, that both the combination of high-level processing and tasks involving complex conceptual judgements is critical for producing more dichotomous awareness patterns. It is also important to note that the level of processing effect on subjective awareness in previous studies has typically

been very small (Anzulewicz et al., 2015; Binder et al., 2017; Windey et al., 2013) and not necessarily observable in accuracy performances (Binder et al., 2017)

A future direction within the *levels of processing* framework should explore the behavioral patterns and neural correlates of stimulus processing at the highest end of the spectrum by using high-level tasks while controlling the presence or absence of conceptual level decision-making processes. An experimental design including stimulus at the letter/number vs. meaning levels of representation, and tasks involving the mere identification opposed to higher-level conceptual categorization and cognitive judgements of the stimulus may shed light into the open questions left by the present findings.

In conclusion, our results show that, contrary to the predictions of the *levels of processing* hypothesis (Windey & Cleeremans, 2015), stimulus processing at both low (energy) and high (letter/number) levels of representation may follow a gradual increase in visual awareness. Interestingly, we found evidence that awareness levels modulate N200/VAN amplitudes only for low-level stimulus processing, whereas in the P3/LP time-window, the amplitudes associated to the different degrees of awareness correlated with the observed graded behavioral (subjective ratings and accuracy) output at both low and high-levels of stimulus processing. The finding that the early posterior correlate of visual awareness (VAN at 150-250 ms) was sensitive to level of processing task manipulation is consistent with the findings that the task effects occur in the visual cortex (Binder et al., 2017) and supports the view that it is mediated by attention to task-relevant features.

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Figure 1. a) Example of Targets, b) Catch trial, c) Mask organizations and d) Mask composition.

Figure 2. Sequence of events: a) detection task, b) identification task.

Figure 3. Example of mask subtraction process in occipital electrode cluster at SOA of 13 ms in the detection task. In order to separate activity evoked by the target from activity evoked by the mask (i.e. Target-only), Mask-only waves were subtracted from Target + Mask waves at each SOA and task conditions.

Figure 4. Awareness distributions in detection and identification tasks: a) reported awareness ratings (% of trials) across SOA conditions (detection), b) intermediate ratings (% of trials) across SOA conditions (detection), c) reported awareness ratings (% of trials) across SOA conditions (identification), d) intermediate ratings (% of trials) across SOA conditions (identification), e) intermediate rating comparison (% of trials) between tasks. Error bars represent standard deviations. $*p < .05$

Figure 5. Accuracy performances in detection and identification tasks: a) detection accuracies (proportion correct) at each awareness rating (SOA 13 ms), b) detection accuracies (proportion correct) at each awareness rating (SOA 27 ms), c) identification accuracies (proportion correct) at each awareness rating (SOA 27 ms), d) identification accuracies (proportion correct) at each awareness rating (SOA 40 ms).

Figure 6. ERPs related to the different awareness ratings in occipital (O1, O2, PO7, PO8) and parietal-occipital (P3, P4, PO3, PO4) electrodes for both detection and identification tasks at the matched SOA of 27 ms.

Table 1. Use of awareness ratings (% of trials) and accuracy levels (proportion correct) at each awareness category in the detection and identification tasks.

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

Figure 6

Table 1

Use of awareness ratings (% of trials) and accuracy levels (proportion correct) at each awareness category in the detection and identification tasks.

Behavioral results in detection and identification tasks

Task	Awareness scale							
	<i>1-no perception</i>		<i>2-weak perception</i>		<i>3-almost clear</i>		<i>4-clear perception</i>	
	<i>Awareness</i>	<i>Accuracy</i>	<i>Awareness</i>	<i>Accuracy</i>	<i>Awareness</i>	<i>Accuracy</i>	<i>Awareness</i>	<i>Accuracy</i>
Detection								
SOA-13 ms	67%	0.32	25%	0.68	6%	0.89	2%	0.97
SOA-27 ms	38%	0.35	30%	0.79	21%	0.95	11%	1.00
Identification								
SOA-27 ms	41%	0.25	36%	0.48	17%	0.78	6%	0.94
SOA-40 ms	18%	0.24	39%	0.54	28%	0.84	15%	0.96

